

An Uncommon Localization of an Atypical Lipomatous Tumor/ Well-Differentiated Liposarcoma: A Case Report and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Liposarcoma is one of the different types of sarcomas. It can be encountered at any age and can remain insidious for a long time. It is easily confused with a lipoma; hence the importance of the immunohistochemical study, which allows us to distinguish between the two entities and to type the liposarcoma. Here, we report the treatment of an atypical lipomatous tumor/well differentiated liposarcoma in an atypical temporal localization in a subject aged 54 years, from diagnosis to treatment with a review of the literature.

Keywords: Atypical lipomatous tumor/ Well-differentiated liposarcoma; Immunohistochemistry; Temporal localization

INTRODUCTION

Liposarcomas are malignant tumors of adipocyte differentiation. They generally occur in adults between the ages of 50 and 65, particularly in men. Liposarcomas can occur anywhere on the body but are very rare in the head and neck region.

CASE REPORT

A 54-year-old patient was operated two times in 2016 in a private structure for a temporal lipomatous mass, of which the anatomopathological study concluded a lipomatous sarcoma. Sent to the oncology department, he was lost of sight till seven years later when he came to our department for the reappearance of a left temporal mass on the same operative site.

The clinical examination found a soft, painless mass without thrill, beat and inflammatory signs [Image 1].

The patient underwent ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) that showed two fusiform intramuscular temporal adipose atypical masses, suggesting recurrence [Image 2].

A surgical excision of the tumor was performed under general anesthesia and the anatomopathological revealed an atypical lipomatous tumor/well differentiated liposarcoma.

After that, the patient received 33 radiotherapy sessions. One year later we retrieved a clinical regression of the temporal mass; CT and MRI examinations did not show no abnormalities [Images 3 - 4]

Image 1: Lateral and frontal view before surgery showing a slight tumefaction in left temporal region.

Image 2: Axial MRI showing two fusiform intramuscular mass in the left.

Image 3: Lateral and frontal view one year after surgery and radiotherapy

Image 4: One-year postoperative axial MRI showed no abnormalities.

Image 5: Histological Pictures

- H.E. GX10, H.E. GX20, H.E. GX40 showing mature fat with band of fibrotic stroma containing spindle cells with enlarged hyperchromatic nuclei (green arrow on H.E. GX40)
- Immunostaining MDM2

DISCUSSION

Sarcomas in the head and neck region are a very rare pathology in adults, while they are more frequent in the pediatric population (35%).^[1-2]

Well-differentiated liposarcomas/atypical lipomatous tumor constitute approximately 40 to 45% of all liposarcomas. They occur predominantly within the peritoneum and limbs [15].

Head and neck liposarcomas (HNLS) account for less than 5% of liposarcomas [3] and 2–9% of all sarcomas that arise in the region [4-5].

The rarity of HNLS is clearly demonstrated by the small number of cases reported in the major series, such as the 30 cases in the 60-year period of MD Anderson Center [5] and the 9 cases reported in the 30-year interval series of the Mayo Clinic [6].

The temporal location is extremely rare.

Liposarcomas are classified into several subtypes, including Atypical Lipomatous Tumor/Well-Differentiated Liposarcoma (ALT/WDL), which is further subdivided morphologically into lipoma-like, sclerosing, inflammatory, and spindle cell variants, dedifferentiated Myxoid/Round-cell; Pleomorphic; and Mixed-type liposarcoma [7].

Well-differentiated liposarcomas are believed to predominate in middle-aged men and are often presented as slow-growing, painless masses [8].

Lipomas are usually present as painless, mobile, and well-defined masses, and rarely pose diagnostic problems for the pathologist. However, deep lipomas or lipomas with atypical features may be mistaken for liposarcoma [9].

Well-differentiated liposarcoma must be difficult to differentiate from benign lipoma due to its indolent course, and histopathological examination is necessary to establish a definitive diagnosis [10]. The terminology ‘Atypical lipomatous tumor’ is preferred than ‘well-differentiated liposarcoma’ for those located in the periphery because they don’t present any risk of metastasis unless they progress to a dedifferentiated liposarcomas [15].

Imaging studies are particularly useful for assessing the size, extent and location of the tumor and its relationship to adjacent neurovascular structures in head regions [9].

Ultrasound findings are not always accurate in lipomatous lesions; CT and MRI can contribute significantly to differentiating lipoma from liposarcoma prior to surgery [11]. MRI shows soft tissue delineation and clearly defines the lesion boundaries in relation to subcutaneous tissue compared to CT. Infiltrative margins are more evident on MRI with fat suppression techniques [12].

Among the many lipomatous lesions, radiological differentiation between a lipoma and a well-differentiated liposarcoma is difficult [9]. A distinct, well-encapsulated, homogeneous fatty mass with few or no septa and little or no enhancement or high T2 signal is a lipoma [8]. A simple lipoma is also made up of fibrous septa, muscle fibers, areas of blood vessels, and inflammation. These non-adipose components can mimic the features of a well-differentiated liposarcoma. Radiological signs suggestive of liposarcoma include non-adipose masses, thick or nodular septa (>2 mm thick), prominent foci with low T2 signal and prominent areas of enhancement [8].

A study by Kljjanienko et al. on fine needle aspiration in liposarcoma demonstrated the difficulty in distinguishing lipomas from well-differentiated liposarcomas due to the morphological overlap in cytological smears [13].

Macroscopically, well differentiated liposarcomas are a lobulated circumscribed fatty mass. Histologically, the predominant subtype is the lipoma-like subtype. It’s composed by mature adipocytes lobes with variable focal intersection made up of fibrous septa of low to moderate cellularity. There are at least focal spindle cells showing atypia.

Liposarcomas usually express the MDM2 and CDK4 antibody by immunostaining (97%). There is a strong correlation with gene amplification of MDM2 and CDK4 [15].

The treatment modalities for lipomas can be divided into non-excision and excision techniques [11]. Most lipomas can be observed without treatment if they are small and asymptomatic. Excision is necessary in cases of diagnostic dilemma, exponential growth, size greater than 10 cm, deep anatomical localization, associated pain, or aesthetic problems [9].

Well-differentiated liposarcomas require wide local excision with clean margins. Recurrence rates increase with incomplete excision, as liposarcomas are often mistaken for benign lipomas [9]. The extent of excision in head and neck lesions has been limited by the proximity of vital neurovascular structures, which may prevent surgeons from performing a wider resection with negative margins. Nonsurgical treatment modalities such as radiotherapy or chemotherapy are of limited use and remain controversial in liposarcoma. Well-differentiated liposarcomas are considered low-grade malignancies, with little or no tendency to metastasize and a good prognosis [14].

CONCLUSION

Liposarcoma of the temporal region remains an extremely rare tumor. A well-differentiated liposarcoma can mimic a lipoma in its clinical presentation. A rigorous clinical, radiological (preferably CT or MRI) and histopathological examination must be performed to avoid incomplete resection and prevent tumor recurrence.

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